

INTERFACIAL DEGRADATION OF STRAINED GLASS FIBER-MATRIX IN ACIDIC SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

The cross-section of glass cloth-vinylester resin composite was degraded in the immersion of acidic and alkaline solution. The composite was always set with desirable strains during the immersion and SEM observation on the cross-section. The strain was found to induce the crack propagation in the bundle of filaments. Such a crack was seen to come from the debonding between glass filament and resin. As a result, the interfacial reinforcement inhibited the debonding, but prompted the crack propagation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) are extensively used in the chemical process industry for applications such as pipework, reaction vessels, storage tanks, pumps, fans, etc. During service, GFRP components are exposed to different chemical environments under load.

In most environments GFRP is reasonably inert, especially when it is covered with resin for anti corrosive layer. The chemical resistance of GFRP is generally evaluated by the retention of strength in the immersion test (ASTM C 581), under the condition that the penetration of acid is restricted. This often leads to misunderstanding in the evaluation of the results.

Acid corrosion phenomenon, called environmental stress cracking, is well known in E-glass fibers, one of the constituents of GFRP [1]. Acid diffusion into matrix resin, however, does not occur without load, as reported [2]. The only combination of these phenomena will not come to thorough understanding of acid corrosion of GFRP. This implies that GFRP can be easily fractured at a fairly low stress, as compared with its original strength, by developing cracks to allow the rapid transport of acid in the resin, as reported by Hogg and Hull [3]. The damage, locally developed in the GFRP even at a low stress, enables acid to penetrate through the resin. This results in acid attack on the fibers and drop of the bond strength at fiber/matrix interfaces.

To clarify the degradation process in GFRP, it should be necessary to use GFRP uncovered with anti-corrosive resin, extremely damaged on the composite, mechanically loaded. If not so, it is difficult to detect the initial degradation. In this study, the cross-section is in contact with acidic

and alkaline solution. After the immersion, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is employed to detect the debonding between glass filament and matrix resin and micro-cracking in the bundle of glass cloth. This procedure makes it clear to see the weakest location on the cross-section formed by glass, resin, and the interface. In addition, the composite is given different strains by tensile load in order to examine the change of degradation processes with tensile stress of the composite.

2. MATERIALS

The glass fiber reinforced vinyl ester laminates used in this study were fabricated by hand lay-up method. Surface treated plain woven E-glass cloth (YEM2103) was supplied by Mie Textile Ltd., Japan. Three types of surface treatment of glass fiber were listed in Table 1. Acryl silane treatment was a model of chemically reacted glass fiber-matrix interface. Heat-cleaned treatment was a model of mechanical contact glass fiber-matrix interface. Epoxy silane treatment is a model of non-chemical reaction with glass fiber-matrix interface. Each laminate contained 2 plies of woven fabric arranged. By the way that the warp and weft directions of the fabric were aligned to the longitudinal and transverse directions of the laminates, respectively. All the laminates were post-cured at 80°C for 2 hours.

Table 1 Materials

Matrix Resin	Vinylester (R806)
Glass Fiber	E type Glass Cloth
Surface Treatment	1. Acryl-Silane 2. Epoxy-Silane 3. Heat-Cleaned

3. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The test sequence was shown schematically in Fig. 1. Molded GFRP was cut for 20 × 5 mm, and polished for sample section. The sample was set on a tension loading apparatus as shown in Fig. 2. In the experiment, 0, 2000, 4000, 6000 μ of tensile strain were set for each composite. Tensile loading condition was controlled with strain signal from strain gage which was adhered to sample surface. In the next stage, the samples were immersed in several environments with keeping tensile strain. Table 2 summarizes environmental conditions. After that, SEM observation was performed under the strain-keeping condition. The focus was set on weft fiber of sample cross-section. A SEM apparatus used was S-2460N (Hitachi, Ltd.).

Fig. 1 Test sequence

Fig. 2 Tension-loading apparatus

Table 2 Environmental condition

	Temperature	Solution	Treatment Time
Acid	R. T.	5% HNO ₃	15min.
Alkali	R. T.	5% NaOH	30min.
Water	R. T.	H ₂ O	60min.
Air	R. T.	—	—
Strain	0, 2000, 4000, 6000 μ strain		

4. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

4-1 Long time immersion without load

The cross-section of GFRP was degraded without strain. In this case the initial degradation was expected to occur at the weakest location on the cross-section. The degradation example was shown in Fig. 3. The photograph clearly showed that the fiber diameter decreased with the immersion time. As glass fiber, matrix resin and interface was directly contacted with environmental solution, the initial degradation began at the interface between glass fiber and matrix resin. This degradation at the interface was proceeded very quickly, and then environmental medium corroded glass fiber at the circumference of glass filament. It should be noted that the fiber surface near the center was not corroded in spite of the direct chemical attack on the surface. This suggested that the interfacial location of glass filament was different from the bulk glass component.

In this experiment under no load on the composite, it was significantly difficult to detect the debonding between glass filament and matrix resin in the initial degradation. The tensile load for the composite was expected to detect such a debonding during the degradation.

Fig.3 SEM photographs of long time immersion samples
(acryl-silane-treated / 50°C / acid)

4-2 Acryl-silane treatment

4-2-1 macroscopic observation

In order to observe the degradation under tensile load, each composite was set with different strains before the immersion in the environmental medium.

Fig.4 shows SEM photographs of acryl silane-treated samples immersed in different environments under strain-keeping conditions.

In the air condition, the damage was not detected below the 6000 μ strain. In other environmental conditions such as water, acid and alkali without strain, the damage was not also detected. But, under the strain-keeping condition, we can easily detect cracks initiation in the weft fiber bundles. In water environment, the occurrence of cracks needed 6000 μ strain. But, in acid and alkali environments, cracks occurred at only 2000 μ strain.

From SEM observation, it was clear that the debonding or crack feature was affected not only by environment condition but also by strain. The crack propagation was mainly observed on strain-keeping samples. This meant that the degradation process was changed with magnitude of strain.

Fig.4 SEM photographs of acryl silane treated composites at several environments

4-2-2 microscopic observation

Fig.5 shows SEM photographs of the cross-section of composites immersed in alkaline solution. Cracks occurred in the weft fiber bundle across the loading direction. This evidence was different from static immersed samples. The degradation of strained sample came from the debonding of fiber-matrix interface. The adjacent debondings were linked each other and then were grown to cracks. Static long time immersed sample were degraded in the all of fiber-matrix interface; as shown in Fig. 3. From the observation of exposed cross-section, the damage pattern under load was different from that without load. The loading condition enlarged interfacial debonding to cracks quickly.

The debonding opening decreased with the appearance of cracks. As a result, no other large crack was produced near the clear crack.

This meant that the strain of sample was absorbed by large cracking area.

As mentioned above, the most weak point of GFRP was fiber-matrix interface irrespective of

magnitude of. Interfacial degradation was able to penetrate environmental medium into inner GFRP. Adhesion strength at fiber-matrix interface seems to affect GFRP degradation.

In previous paper⁴⁾, one of authors described that the existence of cracks is necessary for acid transport, and the combination of cracks and acid accelerates the degradation in GFRP. The crack propagation was found to depend on stress distribution on cross-section.

Fig.5 SEM photographs of debonding and crack (weft)
 debonding : acryl-silane / alkali / 2000 μ strain
 crack : acryl-silane / alkali / 4000 μ strain

4-3 Heat-cleaned treatment sample

Fig. 6 shows the SEM photographs of heat-cleaned samples which have weak interfacial strength. Heat-cleaned sample was more cracked by polishing process in the weft fiber bundle. The crack density in weft fiber bundle increased with the strain-keeping in acid environment. This crack feature was very different from acryl silane-treated sample. The surface treatment reflected the initiation of crack

Fig.6 SEM photographs of heat-cleaned-treated composite at acid environment

4-4 Crack development process

We propose crack development process consisting of four steps in the degradation, as showed in Fig.7. The first, the micro-debonding at fiber-matrix interface occurs in weft fiber bundle. The second, the debonding is opened by enlargement with load. The third, the debondings are linked with neighboring debonding space. The fourth, the linking debonding area are grown up to cracks. The evidence of the lips in crack proves that crack is linked with neighbor debonding, as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig.7 Degradation model

5. CONCLUSIONS

1. The environmental solutions attack to the interface at first, and it becomes the start of degradation on GFRP.
2. Initial degradation depends on surface treatments.
3. Crack propagation depends on the strain of composite.
4. The dependence of environmental solution on degradation are clearly shown from the observation under strain-keeping condition.

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